

DEVELOPMENT, PRODUCTION, CALCULATION AND TESTING OF A CARBON/KEVLAR FIBRE REINFORCED FLAP

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As an extension of the experience with advanced composite structures gained during the development of several components, a trailing edge flap is designed, produced and tested.

The flap consists of fibre reinforced epoxy sandwich panels and solid laminate parts. The suspension and hinge brackets are full carbon epoxy components.

Assembly mainly is carried out by bonding. Only the brackets and the bottom panel are mechanically fastened to the main assembly.

The static test component failed at 1.28 * Limit Load.

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INTRODUCTION

In 1974 Fokker started a program whose aim was the development of aircraft components in advanced fibre reinforced composite materials. This development is in fact an extension of the experience with glass fibre composite materials gained over the past 25 years with cabin interior, radomes; fairings and protection panels. At this moment in this program the following components have been developed:

- Nose wheel doors F28
- Schematic speedbrake
- Speedbrake F28
- Schematic flap
- Main undercarriage leg fairing A300
- Main undercarriage leg fairing and hinged door A310
- Several components designed in aramid material

Not included in this list are the developments of the space division. A short review of the above mentioned components will be given before the more detailed review of the schematic flap.

Nose wheel doors F28

Fig. 1

The nose wheel doors consist of a nomex honeycomb core with carbon fibre/epoxy skins and aramid/epoxy edge members. For interchangeability reasons the existing metal parts have been applied. Dimensions are approximately 1550 x 350 mm. Composite mass (inclusive finish) is 4,82 kilogrammes i.e. a weight saving compared with the metal doors of 23%. Six doors have been manufactured. One door has been submitted to a static test. Failure occurred at 2,3 x ultimate load. A second door has been severely fatigue tested. Total number of cycles achieved was: 894859 with a load upto 1.4 x ultimate load on a door with artificial damages. (honeycomb failed). Two sets of doors have been installed on aircraft for operational trials in Australia and Sweden. Total number of flights about 14000 or 12000 hours (1/3/80). The doors showed a very satisfactory behaviour.

Schematic speedbrake

Fig. 2

The development of a schematic speedbrake preceded the manufacturing of a "flying" speedbrake. For the development of this schematic speedbrake, the shape of the actual speedbrake was changed in such a way that it retained all the unique design and production details of the correctly contoured article. The design is a full composite construction. Overall dimensions, inclusive hinge arms are approx. 1700 x 780 mm. Two schematic speedbrakes have been manufactured. One has been statically tested and failed at 1.73 x ultimate load. The second article has been fatigue tested at 65% ultimate load during 10^6 cycles. The only damage consisted of two small cracks in a bond layer. After repair and introducing artificial damages the test was continued at the same load level. Some additional damage could be determined after 380.000 cycles.

Speedbrakes F28

Fig. 3

The design and adapted materials of the "flying" speedbrake are the same as for the schematic one. The composite mass is 20,8 kilogrammes i.e. a weight saving of 23% compared with the metal speedbrake. Overall dimensions, inclusive hinge arms, are approx. 2200 x 1250 mm. One door has been manufactured and installed on an N.L.M. F28 aircraft for operational trials. Total number of flights is about 3300 or 2600 hours (1/4/80) without any damage.

Schematic flap

Fig. 4

The development of a composite wing trailing edge flap has been chosen because it represents highly loaded and complicated parts. Only the schematised forebody of the double slotted flap has been designed in order to reduce cost. This development is the subject of the more detailed review hereafter.

Main undercarriage
leg fairing A300

Fig. 5

The redesigned main undercarriage leg fairing had to be fully interchangeable with the metal door. The main part of the fairing consists of a sandwich panel with a honeycomb core and reinforced with two carbon fibre hat stiffeners. The overall dimensions of the fairing are approx. 2400 x 1300 mm. Two doors have been manufactured. One door has been statically tested and failed at 1.46 x ultimate load. After repair this fairing was tested in fatigue at 34,6% ultimate load and 83% ultimate load, 200,000 cycles each. No damage was determined. An additional test is under discussion. The second fairing is installed on an A300 aircraft of Air France. The fairing showed a very satisfactory behaviour during about 1000 flights (900 hours) as reached per 1/4/80.

For the A310 production aircraft the main undercarriage leg fairing, which is similar to the above mentioned A300 fairing, is designed in composite material. In addition to this the smaller hinged door will also consist of composite material. Two different wing fuselage fairings for the F28 have been manufactured and installed for operational trials. The behaviour of the fairings is very satisfactory. For the A310 the flap track fairings are being developed in aramid material.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE FLAP

Design

Basic criteria for the design of the flaps are:

- Simplified contours to lower tooling costs
- Simply supported suspension with an overhang at one support
- Connections by means of adhesive bonding, rivets and bolts
- Reduction of the number of detail parts
- Full composite construction
- Interchangeable brackets
- Resistance to lightning strike and impact not taken into account (separate research programs)
- In order to reduce costs only three tab hinge brackets to be designed

An investigation of several alternative designs showed the following typical cross-section (fig. 6) to be the most attractive.

Typical cross-section
of composite flap

Fig. 6

Apart from support and tab hinge brackets, the flap consists of a top skin with integral front- and rearspar, a leading edge, a trailing edge, a bottom skin panel and four ribs.

The topskin consists of a 7 mm nomex honeycomb core with adhesively bonded precured carbon fibre skins. During the bond cycle the spars are cured and bonded to the top skin panel.

Except for the outboard-end rib, which is manufactured entirely from aramid fibre, all ribs are made from carbon fibre. The inboard end rib (sta. 1700, fig. 13) has a support bracket for a swivel link as a separate unit bonded to the rib and provisions for a tab hinge bracket. The rib at sta. 2940 has provisions for a tab hinge bracket only. The heavily loaded rib assembly at sta. 4175 consists of two ribs and a connecting part whose contour follows the top skin. Provisions for a fixed forward support, a swivel link and a tab hinge bracket are foreseen. All ribs are bonded to the topskin and to the spars by means of cleats.

The leading edge consists of solid aramid fibre material. At the location of the intermediate ribs there are nose ribs bonded to the skin. The leading edge is bonded to a recess in the topskin and to the lower flange of the frontspar. The ribs are bonded to the frontspar web.

The trailing edge consists of a nomex honeycomb core with aramid fibre skins, manufactured as two parts and bonded together at the rear edge. Ribs are bonded to the skin panels and afterwards the subassy is bonded to the box in the same way as the leading edge.

The lower skin panel consists of a 9 mm nomex honeycomb core with carbon fibre skins. Near the heavily loaded rib, a lower h.c. core and supplemental layers are applied. The holes for the swivel link are milled after assembly of the precured skins and the core. Foam is applied to seal the edges of the holes.

During final assembly the tab hinge brackets and flap support brackets are installed by means of bolts (they are interchangeable items). The lower skin is connected to the box by means of blind rivets and bolts. The flap can be inspected by means of an endoscope through the holes adjacent to the rib at sta. 4175 and the holes in the inboard, outboard and intermediate rib.

PRODUCTION

The main goals to be achieved with the production of the experimental composite landing flap were:

- to extend the manufacturing experience gained to more complicated fibre reinforced parts and assemblies
- to demonstrate possible reduction of parts by utilizing the materials potential to make integrated structures
- to demonstrate the feasibility of one charge complex primary bonding at elevated temperatures
- to extend the knowledge of N.D.I. techniques in the manufacturing phase of composite components.

Production methods for the individual parts were mostly based upon experience of previously manufactured fibre reinforced structures such as schematic and flying speedbrakes. Therefore manufacturing experiments could be limited to the production of the integrated top skin spars assembly and some much smaller complicated parts.

Because of the importance of the heavily loaded adhesive bonded joints, in addition some tests were carried out to verify the feasibility of the proposed tooling for elevated temperature bonding. E.g. a model spar rib assembly was bonded in an oven to test this bonding process.

Component parts

The inner fore-flap is made of carbon fibre and aramide fibre reinforced sandwich panels and solid parts. The exploded view in fig. 7 shows the general lay-out of the flap.

Fig. 7 Exploded view of flap

The solid parts like ribs, angles, brackets, and leading edge skin were made with conventional hand lay-up and autoclave moulding techniques. 120°C Curing T300 - DX 231/DX 137 unidirectional carbon fibre epoxy prepreg and Kevlar 49 - Narmco 550 preimpregnated fabric style 181 - 150 are used for these parts. Bleeder materials absorbed the excessive amount of resin during the curing process. If possible internal bleeding by alternate dry and impregnated weaves decreased resin waste. Male or female tooling for the different products was chosen in order to achieve good bond surface quality. Before assembly milling and drilling of the holes for respectively bushes and tab hinge attachment bolts took place on a boring and milling machine, to realise correct location for reasons of interchangeability.

The torsion box upper panel consists of precured T300 - DX 231/DX 137 carbon epoxy faces bonded to the Nomex core with Redux 312 L adhesive film. During the 120°C autoclave bonding cycle the integrated spars of this panel were cured and bonded simultaneously for reasons of parts count reduction. The lower panel also consists of precured T300 - DX 231/DX 137 carbon epoxy faces bonded to the nomex core with Redux 312 L. The rebates contain precured composite straps and have constant thickness along the span. The aramide fibre reinforced nomex panels for the trailing edge are made in a curing process. The core splices in these panels are provided with FM 33 foam while local reinforcements are filled with foaming paste EC 3500.

Carbon fibre epoxy parts were trimmed by routing with diamond dipped tooling to required dimensions while aramide fibre products were sanded.

Bonded assemblies

The rib assembly at sta. 1700 and the tab hinge bracket assemblies were bonded with Redux 312/4 in an oven cure cycle. The required bonding pressure was realised by clamping. Next the holes for bushes and bolts were milled in accurate positions.

Ribassembly
at sta. 1700

Fig. 8

In this stage the ribs at sta. 2940 and 1700 were bonded to the upper panel and spars with Redux 312 L. During the same cycle both ribs and the parts in between at sta. 4175 were connected to the upper panel, to the spars and to each other. Much care had to be taken to ensure correct positioning of these components with respect to each other and to the external shape. Because of the complex bonding process (achieve pressure and positioning in 3 directions) the job could only be done with clamping devices. Also the nature of the assembly (one-sided open box with ribs extending through the spars) did not allow autoclave curing with the aid of blankets whether preshaped or not.

In addition the adopted process allowed for good possibilities for in-process control of positioning and pressure application. The tooling also allowed for differences in thermal expansion of the 3.30 m. long upper panel with spars and the light alloy assembly fixture. For this purpose the ribs were fixed to the box itself and were able to slide. The various gripping devices, which were provided with cupped spring washers realised a constant pressure during the flow stage of the adhesive. To minimize mismatches between tooling and parts to be bonded, the rigid tooling surfaces were provided with silicone rubber layers. See figs. 9 and 10.

Assembly at
sta. 4175
prior to
bonding

Fig. 9

The oven temperature during the related bonding cycle was kept somewhat below that of the previous manufacturing cycles to avoid adhesive creep due to increase of internal pressure and thermal stresses with subsequent debonding of the panel faces.

Fig. 10 Outline of bonding tooling at sta. 4175

After inspection of the assembly, bronze bushes were shrunk in liquid nitrogen and pressed into the holes at sta. 4175. The possibility of damaging the carbon fibre bearing surface caused by expansion of the bushes during heating forced post-cure installation. The bushes were mounted with sealing compound PR 1436 and reamed afterwards.

Assembly of leading and trailing edges was done in a roomtemperature curing process. EC 2216 A/B connected the nose ribs with the leading edge skin. This epoxy adhesive also fixed trailing edge panels to each other with ribs in between. In this production phase the Kevlar end rib at sta. 5000 was also bonded. Again simple gripping and clamping provided the required bonding pressure. Fig. 11 shows the trailing edge assembly tooling.

Trailing edge
assembly
tooling

Fig. 11

In the final assembly the flap torsion box was closed by fixing the carbon fibre bottom panel with blind countersunk rivets. Bolts were installed locally within the projected flap track fairing. Bolts also fixed the flap and tab hinge brackets to the ribs.

N.D.I.

N.D.I. techniques used for inspection during the production of the 2 test-articles consisted of X-ray photography, holographic interference techniques and impedance-resonance measurements with the Fokker Bond tester. Table 1 gives a survey of these methods and their use. Fig. 12 shows a holographic interference photograph of the flap bottom panels.

	holographic interference	Fokker Bond Tester	X-ray photography	Check for
solid carbon fibre reinforced parts		○		porosity, delaminations
			○	fibre orientation, local deviations in fibre contents
carbon fibre reinforced honeycomb panels	○			debonds
		○		debonds
heavily loaded bondlines		○		debonds
			○	porosities in bondline
remaining bondlines		○		debonds

Table 1 N.D.I. techniques used in production

Holographic interference photograph of flap bottom panels

Fig. 12

ANALYSIS .

Due to the fact that this flap is not a flying article the design load is equal to the ultimate load (U.L.) without any reserve for environmental effects or other additional requirements to be met by a flying component, such as stiffness, impact resistance, etc.

The defined load is a typical aerodynamic pressure distribution for a flap with tab of a supercritical wing. This load distribution is given in fig. 13.

Fig. 13 Load distribution of fore-flap

Although the fore-flap is just a single torsion box with three suspension points the strength analysis is done with a finite element method. This method allows the use of substructures: i.e. the complete structure can be split up in separate parts which can be coupled during the calculation process.

The advantages of this method are:

- . an excellent description of the structure, including cutouts etc. is possible.
- . the influence of changes in laminates and/or structure during the design phase can fairly easily be determined.
- . accuracy with respect to internal load distribution and deflections
- . use of specially developed composite elements such as membrane-, plate bending- and sandwich elements
- . laminate-theory is implemented in pre- and postprocessors
- . a failure criterion is implemented in a postprocessor, so the reserve factors are immediately available.
- . if local changes are needed only a part of the structure has to be recalculated.

A survey of the analysing process is given via a flow diagram with accompanying text.

"Down stream phase" of process

Actions for all basic substructures and mergers:

- a. calculation of the stiffnesses of the laminates used in the particular basic substructure
- b. input of the basic or merged substructure
- c. determination of the stiffness matrix of the basic or merged substructure
- d. decomposition of the stiffness matrix and determination of the internal displacements of the particular substructure with fixed couple-points.

At level 0 there are no new couple-points so the real displacements of the merged substructure at level 0 are known and the upstream phase can be started.

"Upstream phase" of process

- a/b. Calculation of the final displacements and reaction forces at level 1 and subsequently at level 0 for merged respectively basic substructures.
- For every basic substructure:
- c. internal load distribution: bending and torsion moments, normal- and shear-loads (all per unit width)
 - d. normal stress parallel and perpendicular to the fibres and the shear stress
 - e. reserve factors for the fibres and the matrix (for every layer)
- ad a. A good prediction of the stiffness is important due to the strong influence of the deflections on the aerodynamic performance.
 - ad c. The results of the internal load distribution in the various subcomponents as skin panels, ribs, spars and hinge brackets are used for instability calculations (including bending-torsion coupling effects), calculation of the loads on mechanical joints, etc. The strength of the applied bondlayers is not determined via detail finite element method calculations.

Fig. 14

Test rig with component for static test.
 Picture taken at 1.2 * Limit Load during loading up to failure.
 Final Failure at 1.27 * L.L.:

- Run 2: Between 0.9 and 1.0 * L.L. a sharp sound was heard. After unloading the flap was examined with a fibrescope. During this inspection only a loose cold-bonded fillet at rib 4175 was found and this was considered to have caused the sound.
- Run 3: At this run the L.L. was held for a period of five minutes in order to check if the deflection of a loaded composite structure is time dependent.
- Run 6: Up to the failure load no indication of damage initiation could be observed. At 1.28 * L.L. a failure occurred and caused a temporary decrease of the loads on the tab hinge brackets. After a momentary recovery the flap finally collapsed at the same loadlevel.

Evaluation of the failure.

The primary failure was caused by a collapse of the bondlayer between the web of the inboard rib 4175 and an angle profile which connects this rib to the rear spar web. (Fig. 15)

Primary damage:

failure of the bondlayer between the angle profile and the inboard rib 4175

Failure area with bottom panel removed.

Secondary damage:

Severe crack in rear spar web

Cracks in front spar bottom panel and trailing edge

Extensive debonding of top panel faces and sandwich core

Fig. 15

The moment of failure if adversely influenced by the known poor bondlayer-quality, an X-ray photograph shows a debonded area of 20% of the bondlayer surface. After this initial failure the final collapse caused quite a lot of secondary damage (Fig. 15 and 16).

During the inspection of the damaged area it was discovered that the holes for the suspension link in the ribwebs were strongly ovalized (Fig. 17). The most likely cause of this unexpected damage is a slip away of the metal bushes during the several test runs.

After a detail check of all the strain gauge measurements there were strong indications that at the second test run the stiffness of the joint between rib 4175 and the rear spar was already reducing. This damaging process progresses when during a following test run the same or a higher load is applied.

Fig. 16

Fig. 17

Results of the static test

- . a reinforcement of the tab hinge brackets to prevent instability
- . a better locking of the metal bushes to prevent a loose fit
- . a reinforcement of the joint at which initial failure occurred via bolts through both flanges of the angle profile
- . an excellent agreement between the calculated and tested deflections
- . the agreement between the calculated local stresses and those derived from the strain gauges is in general poor
- . strain gauges are very suitable for indicating local stiffness changes

Fatigue test on a full scale component

It is generally known that a flap encounters high daily loads so fatigue is a very important item. Because of the high daily load level it may be possible that the matrix will crack locally. A test programme has been carried out to examine whether this kind of damaging of the laminate, increasing during the flight life, has an adverse influence on the allowable compressive stress of laminates. Upto now only a small reduction has been found. This programme is the subject of another paper presented during this ICCM-III conference.

The full scale fatigue test programme has already been started and the results will be available in August.